

Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,3-disubstituted 1,4-dioxo-10-methoxypyrazino(1,2-a)indoles

Shaista Bano, Shakti R. Ahmed and Akhlaq R. Kidwai

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,3-disubstituted 1,4-dioxo-10-methoxypyrazino(1,2-a) indoles have been prepared by the condensation of 3-methoxyindole-2-carbonyl chloride with the corresponding N-methylamino acid esters. Their ir and uv spectra have also been reported.

Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,3-dimethyl-1,4-dioxo-10-hydroxypyrazino(1,2-a) indole was carried out in connection with studies on the structure of anhydrodethioglistoxin¹. In addition to this, other 10-hydroxypyrazinoindoles have also been synthesized with 3-ethyl and 3-benzyl groups and one without a substituent in this position². All these compounds are cyclic dipeptides incorporating amino acids like N-methylalanine, N-methylbutanoic acid, N-methylphenylalanine and sarcosine. In the present communication, synthesis of some 10-methoxypyrazinoindoles incorporating trifunctional amino acids like N-methyl-tyrosine and N-methylglutamic acid has been described (Table-I).

TABLE I

Compound ^a	Solvent	m.p. ^b °C	Yield %	C	Calcd.%, H	found%, N
1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-3-(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzyl)-1,4-dioxo-10-methoxypyrazino-(1,2-a) indole.	<i>n</i> -butanol	100	41.7	69.21 69.40	5.53 6.00	7.00 7.40
1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-3-(β -carboethoxyethyl)-1,4-dioxo-10-methoxypyrazino-(1,2-a) indole.	methanol	85	64.6	62.78 63.53	5.85 6.31	8.14 8.26
4,5,12,13-Tetrahydro-11-methoxy-5,12-dioxopyrrolidino-(1,2-a) indolo(1,2-d) pyrazine.	methanol	120	31.7	66.65 67.00	5.22 5.61	10.37 9.89

a = all compounds are reported for the first time.

b = all melting points are uncorrected.

O,N-Dimethyltyrosine was prepared from 1-methyl-2-phenyl-5-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-imidazolin-4-one³. N-Methylglutamic acid was prepared by reductive amination (cf. 4) of α -ketoglutaric acid in the presence of methyl amine on Pd/c (10%) at atmospheric pressure. *L*-Proline (BDH) was used as such.

1. J. R. Johnson and A. R. Kidwai, Unpublished observation, (Doctoral thesis, Cornell University, 1950).
2. N. T. Modi, S. R. Ahmed, A. R. Kidwai and J. R. Johnson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 2228.
3. "Synthesis of N-methylamino acids through 1-methyl-2,5-disubstituted imidazolin-4-one", (in press).
4. R. Schoenheimer and S. Ratner, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, **127**, 301.

Following Johnson's method^{2,5} for the synthesis of pyrazinoindoles, one mole of 3-methoxyindole-2-carbonyl chloride in dry ether was reacted with three moles of N-methyl-amino acid ester in dry ether and the pyrazinoindole worked up as described by these authors.

Demethylation of 10-methoxy compounds was affected by heating with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus². The hydroxy compounds gave green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and their ir spectra showed the presence of chelated OH groups. The amide carbonyl absorption is also shifted to lower frequencies due to this chelation (Table II).

TABLE II

IR and UV spectra of 10-methoxy and 10-hydroxypyrazinoindoles

Compounds	UV λ_{max} (EtOH) m μ	=C-OCH ₃ (cm ⁻¹)	IR N-C=O (indole) cm ⁻¹	C=O (amide) cm ⁻¹	C=O (ester) cm ⁻¹	OH (cm ⁻¹)
1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-1,4-dioxo-3-(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzyl)-10-methoxypyrazino(1,2- <i>a</i>)indole.	270, 320	1250, 1075	1685	1640	—	—
1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-1,4-dioxo-3-(β -carboethoxyethyl)-10-methoxypyrazino(1,2- <i>a</i>)indole.	250, 310	1255	1695	1648	1730	—
4,5,12,13-Tetrahydro-11-methoxy-5,12-dioxopyrrolidino(1,2- <i>a</i>)indolo(1,2- <i>d</i>)pyrazine.	250, 310	1235, 1080	1695	1640	—	—
1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-1,4-dioxo-3-(<i>p</i> -hydroxybenzyl)-10-hydroxypyrazino(1,2- <i>a</i>)indole.	—	—	1695	1610	—	3270
4,5,12,13-Tetrahydro-11-hydroxy-5,12-dioxopyrrolidino(1,2- <i>a</i>)indolo(1,2- <i>d</i>)pyrazine.	—	—	1695	1625	—	3170

UV spectra were recorded on Unicam Sp-500 and ir spectra on infracord.

The authors wish to thank the Head of the Chemistry Department for providing the facilities for this work.

Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh.

Received March 24, 1971